

A nested sieve sampler for collecting aquatic invertebrates in rice paddies

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A study of rice field aquatic habitats initiated in 1981 is cataloging invertebrate species in order to construct a foodweb for rice agroecosystems. This foodweb will be a basis for understanding the role of natural pest enemies and how perturbations such as pesticide use may influence populations of rice insect pests.

An aquatic net is the standard collecting device used to collect invertebrates from streams and ponds. But a net cannot be used in puddled fields with heavy clay soils, shallow water, and closely spaced rice plants because it will not pass quickly through the mud. A number of invertebrates -- chironomid larvae, coleopterans, mites, collembolans, small hemipterans, copepods, and the ostracods -- can escape collection. A 25.5- × 15- × 11-cm metal sampler with 4 nested sieves (see figure) has been used at IRRI for 1 year. It fits between rice hills and can be forced through mud.

Nested sieve sampler, side view (A) with 4 detachable nested sieves with 15, 1.5, 0.75, and 0.25-mm mesh diameter (B), developed for collecting aquatic invertebrates in rice paddies at IRRI.

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